

Raman scattering impairments caused by 50G-PON introduction and mitigation techniques

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We explore the impact of stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) in the context of multiple PON generations sharing the same optical distribution network. The 50G-PON, being the last specified ITU-T PON, imposes the use of high launch power to meet strong optical path loss requirements. We show that the XGS-PON upstream could be the first victim of the introduction of 50G-PON since its wavelength spacing maximizes Raman scattering. We exploit a model to describe both in simulation and experimentally the SRS induced depletion on XGS-PON. Assuming that 50G-PON will be deployed on the current passive infrastructure, we also exploit field data to precisely predict the amount of terminations exceeding the requirements. The results show that up to 1.8 dB can be lost on XGS-PON upstream signals, 1.3 dB on the 50G-PON upstream and 0.5 dB on the G-PON upstream, over a distance of 20 km of fiber. Up to 3% of terminations may be affected, according to our field data exploitation. Improving the receivers' sensitivity through either better photodiodes, signal processing or forward error correction could relax the high launch power constraints, and thus the SRS. Deploying an optical splitter at the central office could also limit the power actually launched into the fiber while meeting high split ratios. Finally, decreasing the 50G-PON downstream wavelength seems a possible option to mitigate the Raman scattering.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Passive Optical Networks (PONs) success is now undeniable, with more than 1 billion FTTH/FTTB active terminations around the world. The success of PONs relies on several factors, including, of course, the low cost of its solutions. Future PON solutions must be capable of meeting the current infrastructure requirements. They must also allow for a smooth migration from one generation to the next, considering the amount of terminations. The coexistence among PONs technologies on the same Optical Distribution Network (ODN) is permitted by a properly defined wavelength plan: bidirectional transmissions on a single fiber are assumed, thus at least a pair of wavelength is needed for each technology, i.e. one for downstream (DS) and one for upstream (US). While standards assume different coexistence scenarios, our deployment, as an operator, is based on the use of Multi-PON Module (MPM) transceivers. MPMs are transceivers that embed the Transmitter Optical Sub Assemblies (TOSAs) and Receiver Optical Sub Assemblies (ROSAs) of several PON technologies [1, 2], see Fig. 1. This currently enables our 10 Gigabit Symetric-capable Passive Optical Network (XGS-PON) deployment strategy, which started in 2023 in countries such as France [3]. XGS-PON will smoothly take more and more importance in

the broadband network, while Gigabit-capable Passive Optical Network (G-PON) will remain active for many years to come and copper networks ("x" Digital Subscriber Line (xDSL)) will be fully decommissioned by 2030 in France [4].

Fig. 1. PON coexistence enabled by Multi-PON Modules (MPM).

The context evolved since the early deployments of G-PON, which aimed to push back the throughput limitations of xDSL and offer new kind of services. One of today's European Union objectives is to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emission by 55%

by 2030, compared to 1990. Orange and other companies committed to these objectives and aims to be net zero carbon by 2040 [5]. To prepare the massive deployments of XGS-PON, Orange France decided to increase the ODN split ratio, moving from 1:64 to 1:128. This increases the sharing of equipment in central offices. This allows for a reduction in the overall carbon footprint while adding a new technology [6]. In terms of standards, Class C+ (17-32 dB) of Optical Path Loss (OPL) (sometimes referred to as Optical Budget (OB)) is exploited to cope with the additional losses. While XGS-PON deployment just started, its successor, the 50 Gigabit-capable Passive Optical Network (50G-PON) must also meet carbon footprint reduction objectives while adjusting to the legacy infrastructure. An option is to increase the split ratio as performed with the XGS-PON, but this option also requires meeting a higher OPL class to meet the additional losses. Class D (20-35 dB) specifications already exist regarding G-PON and XGS-PON, but not yet regarding 50G-PON. The reason is that the receivers considered viable for DS 50G-PON are reaching the sensitivity limits despite the high-performance Forward Error Correction (FEC) selected in 50G-PON and the introduction of signal processing in PON [7–10]. Then, one of the options to increase the OPL consists of increasing the DS launch power. Several teams are pursuing this goal, reaching dynamic launch power around 13.3 dBm with packaged devices and 15.3 dBm with a chip-on-carrier configuration (i.e. the semiconductor chip is directly mounted onto a carrier substrate, not packaged) [11–14].

High launch power in optical transmissions could trigger optical non-linear effects such as Stimulated Brillouin Scattering (SBS) and Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS). In [15], the authors showed that below 11 dBm SBS may appear in a 50G-PON context but has a limited impact under operational conditions, as SBS is affected by the spectral width of the modulated optical signal. Regarding SRS, an energy transfer between multiple signals occurs when a) signals propagating in the fiber show high power and b) their optical frequency difference is close to the maximum of SRS spectral efficiency (13.2 THz). This is the case in the previously described context, because of a) the high launch power of 50G-PON and b) the difference between the DS 50G-PON and US XGS-PON, which is about 12.7 THz. Moreover, in O-band, the non-linear effects are more easily revealed compared to C-band, since the effective area of the mode in Standard Single-Mode Fiber (SSMF) is nearly 20% narrower. Additionally, Kerr-related non-linear effects such as four-wave mixing are enhanced by the nearly null Chromatic Dispersion (CD) close to the zero dispersion wavelength. This article extends our prior work related to SRS in PON [14, 16], with developments in theoretical, experimental, and field analysis.

In Section 2, we describe the industrial context concerning launch power and wavelength planning. Section 3 provides a theoretical description of the SRS, which will be utilized in Section 4 along with experimental results. In Section 5, we exploit the field data collected from G-PON deployed infrastructure to forecast the SRS penalty concerning the amount of terminations impacted. Finally, in Section 6 we discuss the methods to mitigate SRS in the PON context.

2. INDUSTRIAL CONTEXT

A. Launch power

The SRS originates from the interaction of the transport medium, the optical fiber, and the propagating optical signals, in the context of high optical powers, in a process of inelastic scattering

of photons by matter. In the PON context, the specified launch power is provided as a range that depends on the technology, the OPL class, and the direction (US or DS). Legacy G-PON and XGS-PON technologies, when they are the only ones to coexist, do not suffer from such impairments thanks to their relatively low power (below 11 dBm, see Table 1) and wavelength plan. SRS impairments were studied in the context of International Telecommunication Union (ITU-T) Next-Generation Passive Optical Network 2 (NG-PON2) introduction [17], but the technology was finally not selected for massive deployment and will not be considered here.

Then, the problem of SRS in the context of ITU-T PONs has emerged with the deployment of 50G-PON and the associated high launch optical power, as summarized in Table 1. Class D specifications are still For Further Study (FFS) as of this writing. However, the emitted power at OLT is expected to exceed class C+ specifications by at least 3 dB, of which the upper bound is already 14 dBm in DS. Moreover, OLT launch power was increased by 4 dB between class B+ (10 dBm) and class C+ (14 dBm), and by 3 dB between class N1 (11 dBm) and class C+ (14 dBm). Thus, one can assume that the upper bound for class D 50G-PON DS would be about 17 dBm or 18 dBm. Eye safety indicates no risk in the O-band below +22.2 dBm [18]. Regarding US, ITU-T recently agreed on C+ US specifications [19], assuming a launch power as high as 11.8 dBm to address sensitivity impairments at such high baud rates. The class D 50G-PON-US specifications are still FFS.

B. Wavelength plan

SRS is more efficient in the presence of high optical power and when the optical frequency difference between two signals is close to the maximum of SRS spectral efficiency. Fig. 2 summarizes the ITU-T wavelength plan. The so-called "US3" option (1284-1286 nm) is the currently preferred 50G-PON-US solution, as it enables the coexistence with both G-PON and XGS-PON legacy technologies. The 50G-PON-DS wavelength range goes from 1340 nm to 1344 nm.

Fig. 2. ITU-T PtMP optical systems wavelength plan enabling coexistence. NG-PON2 wavelength plan is not reported as it represents a minority of the operational implementation.

The typical Raman gain g_R of SSMF, depending on the optical frequency shift, is represented on Fig. 3, in black. The Fig. 3 also shows the frequency shift combinations between two PON technologies among G-PON, XGS-PON, and 50G-PON in DS or US. Among the 15 possible combinations, four combinations show a Raman gain greater than 20% of the maximum, as represented

Table 1. Synthesis of ITU-T launch power and operating wavelengths. OPL class N1, E1 and E2 values are marked with a star (*). Class B+: 13-28 dB. Class C+: 17-32 dB. Class D: 20-35 dB. Class N1: 14-29 dB. Class E1: 18-33 dB. Class E2: 20-35 dB. Sources: [19–22]

Technology	Direction [rate in Gb/s]	Class B+ or N1* launch power (dBm)	Class C+ or E1* launch power (dBm)	Class D or E2* launch power (dBm)	Operating wavelength (nm) (see also Fig. 2)
G-PON	DS [2.5]	1.5-5	3-7	6-10	1490 ± 10
	US [1.25]	0.5-5	0.5-5	0.5-5	1310 ± 10 (narrow)
XGS-PON	DS [10]	1-4	5-8	8-11	1577 + 3/ – 2
	US [10]	4-9*	4-9*	4-9*	1270 ± 10
50G-PON	DS [50]	4.5-10 (5.5-11*)	8.5-14	FFS (max. 17-18?)	1342 ± 2
	US [12.5]	4-9*	4-9	FFS	1286 ± 2 or 1270 ± 10 or 1300 ± 10
	US [25]	5-9*	5-9	FFS	1286 ± 2 or 1270 ± 10 or 1300 ± 10
	US [50]	6.8-11.8*	6.8-11.8	FFS	1286 ± 2 or 1270 ± 10 or 1300 ± 10

Fig. 3. Raman gain g_R for three PON combinations (the interaction of 50G-PON US with G-PON US is not represented).

in Fig. 3: the 50G-PON-DS interaction with either XGS-PON-US (red), 50G-PON-US (blue) or G-PON-US (green) show a Raman gain of 97%, 63% and 29%, respectively. It is worth noting that these interactions involve counter-propagating signals, as we will explain in the next Sections. It is also interesting to note that 50G-PON-US and G-PON-US should also interact. However, as the latter are both US signals, these interactions remain limited to the "trunk" Section of the ODN (see Fig. 1), and non-linear interactions are thus reduced by the splitter/combiner losses.

Then, we will consider only the three types of interactions in the trunk of the ODN, initiated by the high power of 50G-PON-DS. Since 50G-PON-DS has the highest wavelength, its power will gain, while the power of the other three technologies will be depleted in case of coexistence.

3. ANALYTICAL MODEL

In order to support and extrapolate the experimental results presented in the following Section, a theoretical model was exploited. The basic model describing SRS interactions between two counter-propagating signals consists of a system of two coupled Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) [23, 24]:

$$-\frac{dI_{US}}{dz} = -\alpha_{US}I_{US} - g_R\rho(z)\frac{\lambda_{DS}}{\lambda_{US}}I_{US}I_{DS} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dI_{DS}}{dz} = -\alpha_{DS}I_{DS} + g_R\rho(z)I_{US}I_{DS} \quad (2)$$

The index US stands for the upstream signal (low wavelength) and DS for the downstream (high wavelength, specifically the 50G-PON-DS). The terms of "pump" and "signal" usually used in Raman amplification model are avoided since the "signal's" power is higher than the "pump's" power, and as the "pump" actually carries a signal. Thus, $\lambda_{US/DS}$ is the wavelength of the low/high wavelength signal, $I_{US/DS}$ is the intensity of the low/high wavelength signal, and $\alpha_{US/DS}$ is the attenuation coefficient of the low/high wavelength signal. The intensity I and power P are related by the effective area A_{eff} of the mode: $I = P/A_{eff}$. The parameter g_R is the Raman gain coefficient, shown on Fig. 3 which depends on the wavelength difference (frequency shift) of the two signals. $\rho(z)$ is the polarization overlap of the two signals defined as $\rho(z) = (1 + \vec{s}_{US}(z) \cdot \vec{s}_{DS}(z))/2$, where $\vec{s}_{US}(z) \cdot \vec{s}_{DS}(z)$ is the scalar product of the Stokes vectors representing the State of Polarization (SOP) of signals US and DS at position z . Then $0 \leq \rho(z) \leq 1$, and in case for example of orthogonal SOPs $\vec{s}_{US}(z) \cdot \vec{s}_{DS}(z) = -1$.

Equations 1 and 2 can be solved numerically but also analytically assuming that the gain on the DS signal is negligible. This will be confirmed experimentally in the next Section, assuming that its launch optical power is already high. This assumption is sometimes referred to as the "unfilled probe assumption" [17]. By doing so, Eq. 2 can be solved by neglecting its last term. The solution of Eq. 2 can then be substituted in Eq. 1. As a result, the depletion, which quantifies the power loss of the low wavelength signal compared to a case without SRS after a length L of propagation, can be expressed in decibels as:

$$D_{dB} = P_{DS,0} \cdot \frac{K}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{1 - e^{-\alpha_{DS}L}}{\alpha_{DS}} \right) + P_{DS,0} \cdot \frac{K}{2} \int_0^L \vec{s}_{US}(z) \cdot \vec{s}_{DS}(z) e^{-\alpha_{DS}z} dz \quad (3)$$

With $K = 10 \cdot \log_{10}(e) \cdot g_R \cdot \frac{\lambda_{DS}}{\lambda_{US}} \cdot \frac{1}{A_{eff,DS}}$. In Eq. 3, $A_{eff,DS}$ is the effective area of the high wavelength signal, L the length of fiber which separates the two transmitters and $I_{DS,0}$ the intensity of the high wavelength signal launch at $z = 0$. The depletion in dB, D_{dB} , is directly proportional to $P_{DS,0}$, the optical launch

power of the high wavelength signal (in linear scale), specifically the 50G-PON-DS. Under the previous assumptions, D_{dB} does not depend on the launch power of the low wavelength signal $P_{US,L}$ (the "pump" power in the typical Raman gain context), i.e. of the launch power of the upstream G-PON or XGS-PON or 50G-PON.

The second term of Eq. 3 depends on the product of the Stokes vectors, representing the SOP of signals US and DS at position z . In practice, the SOPs of the counter-propagating signals US and DS vary randomly along the fiber because of the birefringence. As a result the average depletion $\langle D_{dB} \rangle$ can be expressed as:

$$\langle D_{dB} \rangle = P_{DS,0} \cdot \frac{K}{2} \cdot \left[\left(1 - e^{-\alpha_{DS}L} \right) / \alpha_{DS} \right] \quad (4)$$

The previous expression does not account for the time-related behavior of the modulated signals. However, since they are counter-propagating, it is assumed that the SRS averages in time, both at a bit or burst time-scale. Thus, only the average launch power is required.

4. EXPERIMENTAL AND SIMULATION RESULTS, AND DISCUSSIONS

Two main effects are expected from SRS. In the first order, the SRS causes an energy transfer which can be seen as a depletion for the upstream signal (low wavelength) and a gain for the downstream signal (high wavelength). In the second order, SRS is also known to impact the quality of the signal in introducing Relative Intensity Noise (RIN), through SRS-induced cross gain modulation.

This Section's purpose is to validate the model and assumptions of Section 3, starting with the independence of SRS from 50G-PON-US launch power (see Section 4.C), the negligible gain of 50G-PON-DS (unfilled probe assumption, see Section 4.E), and the irrelevance of considering the time-related behavior of SRS and related effects, such as RIN introduction (see Section 4.D). The averaging effect of Polarization Mode Dispersion (PMD) is also discussed in Section 4.F. Once these assumptions are confirmed, a multi-channel model encompassing all ITU-T DS/US PON channels is utilized in simulation in Section 4.G.

Before studying SRS, the experimental setup is introduced (see Section 4.A), and the method used to quantify and mitigate the SBS (which is also triggered by high launch powers) is described (see Section 4.B).

A. Experimental setup

The experimental setup consists of two counter-propagating signals. The high wavelength signal (pink elements on Fig. 4) emulates the 50G-PON signal operating at 1342 nm. It is generated by a Pulse Pattern Generator (PPG) operating at 50 Gb/s and amplified before modulating a Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM). The data sequence consists in a Non-return to Zero (NRZ) On-Off Keying (OOK) Pseudo Random Binary Sequence (PRBS) of $2^{31} - 1$ bits. The optical carrier originates from an External-Cavity Laser (ECL) with a 400 kHz linewidth and is amplified by a Thorlabs BOA1132P Booster Optical Amplifier (BOA) confined by two optical isolators, biased at 750 mA and providing more than 20 dBm peak power. A Polarization Maintaining (PM) Variable Optical Attenuator (VOA) adjusts the optical power crossing the Optical Filter (OF) and reaching the optical fiber. Due to the high Polarization Dependence Gain (PDG) of the BOA, PM fiber is used from the ECL output to

the OF input (red on Fig. 4). After propagation in SSMF, the high wavelength signal passes through a circulator and reaches a power meter (Pm) which measures the received power of the high wavelength signal when the low wavelength signal is enabled ("on") or disabled ("off"). The difference is referred to as the "on-off" gain. Alternatively to the power meter, the signal is led to a 200 GSa/s and 60 GHz bandwidth Digital Storage Oscilloscope (DSO) to estimate the Transmitter and Dispersion Eye Closure (TDEC). This method uses eye diagrams to estimate the penalty induced by a transmitter compared to an ideal one.

Similarly, the low wavelength signal (light green on Fig. 4) emulating XGS-PON-US, is generated by a commercially available XGS-PON transceiver and an evaluation board using a PPG operating at 10 Gb/s in NRZ-OOK. The PRBS length is $2^{31} - 1$. A VOA controls the power of the signal reaching the fiber after passing through a circulator. The SOP can be manually adjusted using a Polarization Controller (PC). The OF directs the signal to a power meter that measures the on-off depletion (similarly to the on-off gain), or a receiver (Rx) followed by a Clock Data Recovery (CDR) and an Error Detector (ED) that estimates the Bit Error Ratio (BER).

B. Stimulated Brillouin scattering mitigation

Stimulated Brillouin scattering is of concern when it comes to the quantification of SRS, as SBS reduces the actual power distribution along the fiber and affects both the transmission performance and the SRS efficiency. SBS mitigation is usually performed by shifting in time the wavelength of the optical signal. In practice, sending data at a high rate already shifts the wavelength (through phase-amplitude coupling processes related to transient chirp) and thus mitigate the SBS, it has also been proposed to modulate the signal's amplitude at a low frequency and exploit the laser's inherent amplitude-phase coupling related to thermal chirp [15, 25].

However, this method impacts the data quality [15]. Our setup uses an ECL, which is not suitable for low-cost field deployments but is practical for laboratory experimentation: we avoided any impact of the SBS mitigation method on data quality by exploiting the ECL's features. We chose to modulate the ECL wavelength as proposed in [26], in exploiting an auxiliary input of our ECL. This broadens the linewidth of the incident light to reduce the coherent buildup of the SBS bandwidth before reaching the MZM.

We used a Waveform Generator (WFG) to periodically tune the wavelength of the ECL around the 1342 nm target. The auxiliary input of the ECL was limited to 420 Hz (low pass cutoff frequency) and 9 Volts peak-to-peak, with a tone. Those parameters showed the best performance in terms of SBS mitigation. As a result, the ECL's optical frequency total excursion was 2.8 GHz (about 20 pm), and enabled mitigation of the SBS by 13.5 dB for a launch power of 14 dBm and 40 km of SSMF, see Fig. 5 in green and blue respectively. For the same launch power, when the optical signal also carries 50 Gb/s data, the spectrum broadens, and the SBS can decrease by 23.3 dB compared to the case without SBS mitigation (see Fig. 5 green and yellow). Finally, when both wavelength modulation and 50 Gb/s data modulation are used, the SBS is mitigated by 29.6 dB for 14 dBm launch power (see Fig. 5 green and red). This corresponds to the Rayleigh Backscattering (RBS), as backscattered power is proportional to launch power. In all four curves of Fig. 5, for low launch powers (2-4 dBm), RBS dominates SBS since the launch power is proportional to the backscattered power (RBS is a linear effect). RBS is about 32 dB below the launch power, as expected [27].

Fig. 4. a) Experimental setup. b) Eye diagram of the launched XGS-PON US. c) Eye diagram of the launched 50G-PON DS. Acronyms: Clk: clock generator. PPG: Pulse-Pattern generator. Amp.: electrical Amplifier. WFG: Waveform Generator. ECL: External Cavity Laser. BOA: Booster Optical Amplifier. PM VOA: Polarization Maintaining Variable Optical Attenuator. OF: Optical Filter. Pm: Power Meter. Rx: Receiver. ED: Error Detector. DSO: Digital Storage Oscilloscope. SSMF: Standard Single Mode Fiber. Tx: Transmitter. PC: Polarization Controller. CDR: Clock Data Recovery.

Fig. 5. Stimulated Brillouin Scattering backscattered power in case of no mitigation technique (green), wavelength modulation (blue), 50 Gb/s data (yellow) and both wavelength modulations and 50 Gb/s data (red). 40 km of fiber.

C. Stimulated Raman scattering induced depletion

Achieving high optical launch power (~ 18 dBm) is possible with our setup due to the high saturated output power of the BOA. However, when transmitting data, the BOA saturates and degrades the optical signal quality. Thus, the question arises whether the SRS characterization without data at high power is equivalent to that of a signal carrying 50 Gb/s for the same launch power. Fig. 6.a shows a comparison of the SRS-induced depletion on XGS-PON-US in case of wavelength modulation (blue), 50 Gb/s data modulation (yellow) and both wavelength and data modulations, after 40 km propagation. The wavelength of the signals are 1342 nm for 50G-PON DS and 1270 nm for XGS-PON US (the frequency shift leads to a Raman gain of about 97%). The results show good agreement on the 0-13 dBm range, confirming that SRS characterization is equivalent with or without 50 Gb/s data. Notably, beyond 15 dBm, the theoretical model from Eq. 4 (black dashed line) and the experimental results (blue) diverge. This is assumed to originate from the SBS which induces non-linear attenuation, as SBS becomes significant beyond this point when not transmitting 50 Gb/s data (see Fig. 5).

The SRS-induced depletion was measured for various XGS-PON launch power (see Fig. 6.b), and the experimental results confirm the assumption of Section 3 that it is not needed to consider the XGS-PON launch power.

Similar observations regarding SBS impact were made with fiber length in the range of 2 km to 40 km, see Fig. 7. For a given launch power, e.g. 10 dBm, the agreement between the

Fig. 6. Depletion induced by Stimulated Raman Scattering on XGS-PON-US with 40 km of fiber. In a) SRS in case of wavelength modulation (blue), 50 Gb/s data (yellow) and both wavelength modulations and 50 Gb/s data (red). In b), SRS depending on the XGS-PON launch power.

theoretical model and the experiments is better for short reaches than for long ones and for low launch powers. This confirms the detrimental role of the SBS in SRS characterization. The theoretical model will remain the reference while being fitted with experimental results in the range 2-13 dBm, where SBS does not impact SRS measurements. For the modeling of Figs. 6, 7 and following simulations, we used $g_R = 76 \cdot 10^{-18}$ m/mW, $A_{eff} = 66 \mu m^2$ and $\alpha_{DS} = 0.323$ dB/km, which is in good agreement with [24].

D. SRS induced RIN impact on XGS-PON

As the SRS induces an energy transfer from the low to the high wavelength signal, and as both signals carry data in the coexisting PON context, the varying intensity of one signal can result in RIN on the other, even in a counter-propagating configuration [28]. Assuming that SRS-induced RIN would impact the BER, we measured the 50G-PON impact on the XGS-PON's sensitivity, within the experimentally available 50G-PON modulated launch power range (up to 13 dBm). We used a PIN receiver and measured the BER depending on the Received Optical Power (ROP) at 10 Gb/s, as shown in the setup (Fig. 4). While the receiver's sensitivity is worse than the XGS-PON specifications, the relative variation in sensitivity to the amount of 50G-PON

Fig. 7. SRS induced depletion for different lengths of fiber and launch powers (with wavelength modulation, without 50G data).

can still be estimated. The results, presented on Fig. 8, do not show a significant impact of the 50G-PON launch power on the sensitivity at XGS-PON FEC threshold (10^{-3}) within the considered range (-60 dBm to 13 dBm). Actually, when the ROP reaches high BERs, the receiver's noise is usually dominated by thermal noise in case of PIN photodiode or by shot noise in case of Avalanche Photodiode (APD) (mainly used in PONs) and a small increase in RIN is negligible. For higher ROP, RIN might dominate the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), but the impact would not be sufficient to lower the BER below the FEC threshold in the case of a digital transmission. The impact would then be negligible and thus the SRS-induced RIN will be considered negligible here.

Similarly, no impact was observed regarding the SRS-induced RIN on the other channel (i.e. the 50G-PON-DS), regardless of whether the XGS-PON-US launch power is high or low (with respect to the values of Table 1). The result conforms to the expectations, as the gain, which characterizes the first order of interactions between the two signals, is already quite low, as stated in the next paragraph. Kerr-related effects, such as self-phase modulation which usually impact the signal's quality, were also not observed.

Fig. 8. 50G-PON impact on XGS-PON sensitivity. $L=20$ km.

E. SRS impact on 50G-PON

In Section 3, we made the assumption that the gain on the high-wavelength signal was negligible to derive Eq. 4. The gain of the 50G-PON was precisely measured in automating the experimental setup to improve the precision, with an accuracy of about

0.1 dB. An example is shown by Fig. 9 with 20 km of SSMF. When the 50G-PON power varies from 7.6 to 13.6 dBm and the XGS-PON power varies from 3 to 7 dBm, the experimentally measured gain remains in the range of ± 0.1 dB. This is the range of the measurement uncertainty, explaining why positive and negative gains are measured. The gain was also estimated theoretically by exploiting the system of Eq. 1 and 2. The results, depicted in Fig. 9 in black and red, indicate that the gain should remain below 0.17 dB in the worst case (i.e., 20 km of fiber and 0-20 dBm launch power), and should be neglected.

Fig. 9. Gain induced by the Stimulated Raman Scattering on the 50G-PON. Experimental results in colors, theoretical measurements in black. $L=20$ km.

F. SRS dependence to polarization

So far, we expressed the depletion exploiting the average value provided by Eq. 4. However, the second term of Eq. 3 contains the product of the SOPs of the two signals, \vec{s}_{US} and \vec{s}_{DS} along the fiber. The evolution of the SOP along the fiber is generally considered a random process, driven by the randomly varying birefringence of the fiber, and statistically described by the PMD. In [29], the authors discussed the impact of polarization in the context of Raman amplification, and demonstrated mathematically that the probability density function of the Raman gain follows a Gaussian distribution in decibels, even for two counter-propagating signals. They also showed that the PDG in a counter-propagating Raman amplification scheme was only about three times smaller than in co-propagating scheme. The results of [29] can be transposed in the context of coexisting PONs to determine σ_{SRS} , the standard deviation of the SRS-induced depletion. These are showed on Fig. 10.a for launch of 18 dBm. As PMD increases, the standard deviation of the depletion decreases because the SOPs are "more averaged". For low propagation length, both the depletion and its standard deviation are small.

In practice, the SSMF specifications require the PMD to remain below $0.2 \text{ ps} / \sqrt{\text{km}}$, while the fibers in our laboratory exhibited PMD around $0.07 \text{ ps} / \sqrt{\text{km}}$. In the first case (without SRS), we randomly varied the SOP of the launch XGS-PON using the PC (see Fig. 4) and measured the received power 1000 times. The latter slightly varies around an average value with a standard deviation which we named σ_1 , see Fig. 10.b in blue. The standard deviation of the histogram of the XGS-PON received power is not zero as the manipulation of the PC slightly affects the launch power due to the stress induced on the fiber. In the second case (with SRS), the procedure is repeated introducing the 50G-PON-DS. As a result, the average received power is lower than in the first case due to the mean depletion, but the new standard deviation, named σ_2 , also increases compared to the first case, see Fig. 10.b in red. The reason is that the received

Fig. 10. Depletion's standard deviation dependence to PMD (launch power: 18 dBm, average measured depletion: 1.75 dB).

power is affected by the previous stress induced on the fiber as well as by SRS. Assuming that SRS is independent of the received power variations without SRS, which means assuming that the two processes are independent, and then their standard deviations can be connected as $\sigma_2^2 = \sigma_1^2 + \sigma_{SRS}^2$. Experimentally, σ_{SRS} is about 0.025 dB for a propagation length of 40 km, and a PMD of $0.07 \text{ ps}/\sqrt{\text{km}}$, which is lower than the predictions in [29]. Considering that both the experimental and theoretical expected values are low (below 0.05 dB), and that PMD values lower than $0.01 \text{ ps}/\sqrt{\text{km}}$ or less are unrealistic in practice, we will consider the standard deviation of the depletion to be negligible.

G. Multiple coexisting channels

The previous experiments and models considered the interaction between only two channels. However, when it comes to the PON coexistence scenario, six channels may have to coexist (G-PON, XGS-PON and 50G-PON in both US and DS). The SRS interactions were modeled exploiting a system of six equations similar to Eq. 1 and 2. The losses of the ODN splitters are neglected in the simulations. By doing so, we can estimate the power variation of a channel, e. g. 50G-PON-US, experiencing both depletion from a higher wavelength channel (such as 50G-PON-DS) and a gain from a lower wavelength channel (as XGS-PON-US, see Fig. 2). The results, depicted on Fig. 11 are provided when the launch powers are at their maximum (see Table 1) to maximize the SRS interactions, except for the 50G-PON-DS launch power, which is varied. The considered propagation length is 20 km. On Fig. 11, the blue curves correspond to the XGS-PON-US depletion, the red curves to the 50G-PON-DS gain, the green curves to the G-PON-US depletion, and the purple curves to the 50G-PON-US depletion. In the first step (circles), the depletion and gain are estimated when only 50G-PON-DS and XGS-PON-US coexist. Then, G-PON-US is introduced (triangles) and finally 50G-PON-US is introduced (squares).

While small variations appear in the three different scenarios, they remain below 0.1 dB for the depletion (in blue). Only the 50G-PON-DS gain varies significantly with the introduction of 50G-PON-US from 0.2 dBm to 0.5 dBm (in red), because the 50G-PON-US power is high (11.8 dBm). It is noteworthy to observe the depletion shift for low 50G-PON-DS launch power. For example, at 2.5 dBm, the G-PON-US depletion is negative (green).

The reason is that G-PON-US benefits from SRS-induced gain due to its interaction with the 50G-PON-US, which compensates for the depletion caused by 50G-PON-DS.

In brief, for a 50G-PON-DS launch power of 18 dBm (the maximum mean launch power expected for class D as discussed in Section 2), the SRS-induced depletion is expected to reach 1.8 dB for the XGS-PON-US, 1.3 dB for the 50G-PON-US and 0.5 dB for the G-PON-US, with 20 km of fiber. Since G-PON-DS and XGS-PON-DS operate more than 22 THz away from the other channels, the SRS is negligible (g_R is almost null, see Fig. 3) and we chose not to present related results.

Fig. 11. SRS induced depletion and gain of G-PON-US, XGS-PON-US and 50G-PON-US depending on the 50G-PON-DS launch power (20 km)

5. FIELD DATA EXPLOITATION

Operators collect field data on a daily basis to improve the customer experience in preventing or diagnosing network issues. Among those are data related to optical access physical layer parameters, such as the Optical Line Termination (OLT)-Optical Network Unit (ONU) distance (measured by the OLT to manage the US burst arrivals), or the transmitted and received power (provided by the Received Signal Strength Indication (RSSI)) of the currently deployed G-PON. The point of this Section is to exploit those field data, to estimate the actual number of customers who might suffer from SRS through the introduction of high power transmitters with class D 50G-PON. PON generations might succeed each other, but the currently deployed ODNs will remain the same as the passive infrastructure is by far the major source of expenses in PON deployment and then, today's G-PON ODN optical characteristics are tomorrow's 50G-PON ones. Then, assuming a given launch power of the 50G-PON and knowing the OLT-ONU distance of each pair allows to estimate the SRS-induced non-linear excess loss on other channels, referred to as Optical Path Penalties (OPPs), based on calculations and experiments from previous sections.

The data used here come from a wide sample of the physical layer characteristics of 73000 active terminations and 2000 ODNs, corresponding to about 1% of today's Orange Fiber To The Home (FTTH) customers in France. It includes high- and

low-density areas, making it a representative snapshot of today's infrastructure.

The XGS-PON OPLs are estimated as follows: first, the G-PON OPLs are estimated from the field data using the difference between the transmitted power and the RSSI. The US values are preferred as they tend to show lower OPLs, and then lead more easily to link outages. Secondly, as the US wavelengths of G-PON and XGS-PON are different (1310 nm and 1270 nm respectively), an additional loss is added to each OLT-ONU pair, considering the actual length of each OLT-ONU pair. The estimated attenuation coefficient difference is $\alpha_{XGSPON} - \alpha_{GPON} = 0.044$ dB/km. As a result, the OPLs of each XGS-PON OLT-ONU pair are estimated from the US field data of G-PON, before the actual wide range deployment of XGS-PON. The obtained distribution is displayed in Fig. 12 in blue. A gamma distribution fit is also proposed, given by the form $f(x) = (x - x_0)^{a-1} \cdot e^{-(x-x_0)} / \Gamma(a)$ with $x_0 = 24.0$ dB and $a = 6.15$.

Then, the impact of SRS on the XGS-PON (the OPP) depends on the launch power and the link length. While different split ratios may be considered, the additional splitter may not necessarily be located at the Central Office (CO) side. If located at the CO, the splitter reduces the optical power actually launched in the fiber by the 50G-PON-DS, thereby reducing the SRS impact. Additionally, it is noteworthy that in 90% of the links, the length of the "branches" of the ODN (i.e. the portion of fiber between the ONU and the "remote splitter", see Fig. 1) is less than 2 km. While it is not possible to determine the "trunk" length of the ODN, we will assume that the OLT-ONU distances reported by the field data is the trunk length, as it will also inflate the SRS-induced penalty and correspond to a "worst case" scenario. To summarize, we use Eq. 4 and the distance of each individual OLT-ONU pair from the field data to estimate the upstream estimated attenuation which include the SRS-induced OPP and the OPL, for a given launch power.

Then, we consider the acceptable upper limit of XGS-PON OPL moving from 29 dB (class N1) to 35 dB (class D). However, we also assume the split ratio increases from 1:64 to 1:256, as discussed in the introduction, through the insertion of one or more splitters, adding also 6 dB penalty to the OPL (neglecting the insertion losses). As a result, both effects offset each other.

Fig. 12. Estimated optical path losses distribution of upstream XGS-PON without (blue) and with (red) SRS induced by 50G-PON-DS.

Fig. 12 shows an example of the OPL distribution without SRS (blue) and with SRS (red), including OPL and OPP, for a 50G-PON-DS launch power of 18 dBm. The threshold at 35 dB highlights the number of terminations exceeding the apparent

OPL limitation. The percentage of users exceeding the limitation is about 5% without SRS and 8% with SRS, as shown in Fig. 12. By comparing the two "tails" of the histograms beyond the threshold, it is easy to estimate the amount of terminations exceeding the apparent OPL boundaries solely due to SRS.

The process can be repeated in varying the launch power and the CO splitters losses, as shown in Fig. 13. According to our field data, when the 50G-PON-DS launch power reaches 18 dBm, an additional 3% of our customers will exceed the upper OPL class solely because of SRS. If the power actually launched in the trunk of the ODN is decreased by 3 dB or 6 dB because of a 1:2 or 1:4 splitter at the CO, the number of customers exceeding the upper OPL class will decrease to 1.3% and 0.7%, respectively. While those percentages may seem low and based from a sample, they are to be put into perspective to the millions (or billion) of terminations potentially impacted worldwide, and the potential additional cost and GHG emission required to address the issue.

It is also important to note that those forecasts are made for a specific operator and country, and may vary in other contexts. Also, the RSSI accuracy is specified at ± 2 dB and ± 3 dB in DS and US, respectively [30]. The limited accuracy artificially broadens the histograms, even before introducing the SRS-induced penalty. Generally, improving the accuracy of network data is critical for efficient diagnosis, prevent outages and feed this kind of long-term studies. Additionally, the emitters and receivers of today's deployed network generally exhibit better performance (better emitted power or sensitivity) than expected. They provide additional margins that allow reaching terminations already beyond G-PON specifications, and also partially explain the "tails" of the histograms on Fig. 12. It is uncertain whether these extra margins will be affordable in future PON generations, increasing the need for effective SRS mitigation.

Fig. 13. Percentage of XGS-PON terminations exceeding the high OPL threshold because of SRS-induced by 50G-PON introduction.

6. STIMULATED RAMAN SCATTERING MITIGATION

This Section discusses various options to mitigate SRS in the ITU-T-PON context.

Orthogonal polarization states: it was proposed in the context of NG-PON2, which exploits time and wavelength division multiplexing, to make each downstream wavelength's polarization state orthogonal to the next [31, 32], or more generally to arrange the polarization states so that their weighted Stokes vectors add to zero. As a result, the polarization overlap probability with another channel remains close to 0.5. However, in this article's context, as the interacting signals are counter-propagating and considering the natural PMD of SSMF, this solution is not feasible due to depletion averaging.

Power spectral density shaping: SRS impact has also been

mitigated in the context of optical Cable Television (CATV), using modulation formats such as Manchester, 8B10B, Miller or dicode codings [33–35] or in filtering the low frequency components of the signal. These solutions only mitigate RIN due to the SRS of the analog signal carrying the CATV, and not the depletion itself.

New fibers: recent demonstrations related to new fiber types, such as Hollow Core Fiber (HCF) [36] fill the community with enthusiasm. Low CD, very low attenuation, and limited non-linear effects can be expected from these. However, since the main cost source in PONs is the passive infrastructure and HCF is not yet mature, widely replacing the SSMF with HCF in optical access network does not seem realistic yet.

Alternative wavelength plan: The reason why O-band is so crowded (see Fig. 2) is that Intensity Modulation/Direct Detection (IM/DD) based PON systems require very low chromatic dispersion (up to 3.85 ps/(nm.km) at high baudrate), and try to avoid the use of chromatic dispersion compensation techniques. Moving the 50G-PON-DS wavelength closer to the G-PON-US limit (1320 or 1330 nm for narrow and reduced G-PON options, respectively) could reduce both SRS and CD impairments while maintaining interoperability. Decreasing 50G-PON-DS wavelength by 7 nm corresponds roughly to 10% reduction in XGS-PON depletion, in dB. G-PON is widely deployed today and operators did not all chosen the same wavelength range option, but field results suggest that, in practice, the wavelength distribution of G-PON-US emitters is narrower than the specifications [37]. The reason for such a gap in the wavelength plan is the existence of IEEE-PON technologies utilizing the 1320 nm band in upstream, while the 50 Gb/s IEEE-PON utilizes the same band as 50G-PON in downstream to share the production and cost efforts. At the time of writing, the 50G-PON reached a level of maturity which may limit such wavelength plan evolution.

Reduced launch power: Reducing the launch power of 50G-PON will reduce the SRS impact. However, reducing the launch power by 1 dB decreases the SRS depletion by a fraction of a dB, according to the results presented in Section 4. For example, on Fig. 11, the SRS-induced depletion of XGS-PON-US (blue) is ~ 2 dB for a 18 dBm launch power, and ~ 1 dB for a 15 dBm launch power. The slope is then about $1 \text{ dB}/3 \text{ dB}$. As a curiosity, the threshold for which decreasing the launch power is equal to the same reduction in the SRS-induced depletion (slope = $1 \text{ dB}/1 \text{ dB}$) is obtained in using Eq. 4 and solving $dD_{dB}/dP_{in,dB} = 1$. The result is $D_{dB} = 10/\ln(10) \approx 4.34 \text{ dB}$, which corresponds to a launch power far beyond the context of this study. Thus, reducing the launch power alone is not the solution as a launch power of 15 dBm already corresponds to 1 dB of depletion on XGS-PON-US. Alternatively, avoiding high launch powers prevents from meeting the OPL requirements, while increasing the launch power enhances SRS.

Splitter at the central office side: In the case of an ODN with a high split ratio, we recommend deploying the splitter at the CO side, as discussed in Section 5, to decrease the actual launch power and create two separate ODNs which will only share only a few meters of fiber. Unfortunately, this may not fit all field constraints, as operators have different engineering rules.

Improved sensitivity, FEC or signal processing: as stated in the introduction, the need for increased launch power comes partially from the current limitations of receivers considered viable for PONs. Many research activities are ongoing on improved sensitivity receivers [7, 8] but these solutions are not mature at the time of writing. FEC was optional in the first generations of PONs, but is mandatory in practice since XGS-PON.

Another type of FEC could theoretically improve the sensitivity by a fraction of dB, even though FEC is a major source of power consumption. Finally, similar to FEC, improved equalization techniques could theoretically enhance the sensitivity by a fraction of dB. While the FEC type is already specified in 50G-PON, the equalization technique is neither detailed nor imposed, and only the performance specifications (such as sensitivity) must be met. Generally, creating a new class of ONU with improved sensitivity could be the key to meeting the requirements while avoiding excessive increases in launch power and mitigating SRS.

7. CONCLUSION

As increasing the launch power toward ~ 18 dBm seems a probable solution to meet class D optical path loss, non-linear effects such as stimulated Raman scattering cannot be neglected anymore. We explored the impact of stimulated Raman scattering in a scenario where multiple PON technologies coexist, i.e. when the terminations of the same optical distribution network exploit G-PON, XGS-PON and 50G-PON. XGS-PON upstream channels will be the primary victims of SRS in this context, since the wavelength difference with that of the 50G-PON-DS is at about the maximum of SRS gain. The XGS-PON upstream channel will then experience up to 1.8 dB depletion in the worst case (18 dBm launch power and 20 km fiber). Under similar conditions, the upstream channels of 50G-PON-US and G-PON-US will experience 1.3 dB and 0.5 dB of depletion, respectively. We demonstrated both theoretically and experimentally that the gain perceived by the downstream channel of 50G-PON will be negligible in all cases, since its launch power is already significant. We also demonstrated that the depletion's dependence to polarization is limited when the PMD is higher than $0.01 \text{ ps}/\sqrt{\text{km}}$, since the channels are propagating in opposite directions. Also, the SRS induces a negligible amount of noise through the energy transfer process, which does not affect transmission quality, as the receiver's sensitivity is limited by thermal noise, not by SRS induced RIN.

The G-PON field data were also exploited in order to estimate the impact of the SRS on the actual infrastructure. Since the passive infrastructure is the primary source of cost in FTTH, today's OLT-ONU distances helped estimate that, in the worst case, up to 3% of XGS-PON termination will exceed the high OPL because of SRS-induced by the introduction of 50G-PON. Several SRS mitigation techniques were also examined. Deploying a first optical splitter at the OLT side seems like a good option to limit the actual launch power, but may not fit all field constraints, as operators have different engineering rules. Alternatively, if the receiver's sensitivity at ONU side cannot be improved, the launch power must remain high at OLT side. Assuming that only ITU-T technologies will coexist, decreasing the 50G-PON-DS wavelength closer to the upper limit of G-PON-US (around 1310 nm) seems to be an alternative that meet the OPL class requirements while limiting SRS impact. However, the demonstration and specification of a new class of ONUs with improved sensitivity (through enhanced FEC, responsivity, or signal processing) could relax launch power constraints and reduce SRS impact while meeting class D requirements.

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